

ESFRI

Landmark Monitoring 2022- 2024

Third Batch Report

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OBJECTIVES AND GENERAL REMARKS

ESFRI Landmarks were introduced in the ESFRI Roadmap 2016 as reference Research Infrastructures (RIs) and are pillars in the ERA landscape, offering not only services to academic research but also supporting development and innovation.

In order to support the further development of the Landmarks and to achieve further insights into the functioning of the European RI ecosystem, the Forum has assigned the Monitoring Committee (MC) with the task of conducting a regular monitoring of all ESFRI Landmarks.

The Monitoring should further enable regular exchange between ESFRI and the Landmarks on their long-term development, assess the quality of each individual Landmark, identify possible problems and support the Landmarks to take appropriate actions. It shall also provide information on the performance, output and impacts of the Landmarks.

The pilot round of Monitoring started with a Kick-Off Workshop on 16th September 2022 in Brussels, involving interested stakeholders. The pilot Monitoring round consisted of three batches. The Monitoring rounds will be repeated regularly, maybe around every 5 years, depending to some extent on other ESFRI activities, as this is a time-consuming activity.

Both the first and second batches included 11 ESFRI landmarks and their monitoring was completed with the first batch report in June 2023 and the second batch report in June 2024, respectively.

The present report summarises the results of the Monitoring of the third and final batch comprising 8 Landmarks. The main generic findings are described in chapter two, while the experiences with the third batch of Monitoring are described in chapter three. While the first batch had already shown that the concept worked well in general, experience from this first batch served to optimise some organisational aspects for the second batch, which proved effective in this third batch. For keeping to the overall timeline of the monitoring the third batch was started while the second batch was only halfway through. Increasing experience with the monitoring process of all participating parties allowed finalizing the second batch while the third batch was already running, and finalizing this third batch while the Roadmap 2026 process has already begun. The workload on the Working Groups, especially the IG and the SWG DIGIT that both participate in all Panels, is challenging, even more so when considering that all other ESFRI activities will typically also require the expertise available in these groups.

This report completes the set of three summary reports on three batches of Monitoring. The MC will discuss the Lessons Learnt in the first months of 2025 and deliver a final report mid of 2025.

The distribution of Landmarks over the three batches is given in the annex.

The individual reports will be accessible, only for ESFRI purposes, to delegations via CIRCABC.

The individual reports shall be kept confidential within ESFRI (Forum and Working Groups) and are not made publicly available.

The Monitoring Committee suggests publishing this summary report on the ESFRI website.

MAIN FINDINGS OF THE LANDMARK MONITORING (2023-2024)

Usually RIs have worked together with the Monitoring Panels in an open and constructive way. Hearings were often crucial for understanding the current situation for the Landmarks adequately. There were site visits for two Landmarks, both of the single-sited kind.

- In general, the scientific excellence of the RIs is considered very good or even excellent.
- The Pan-European relevance is good for all, and in several cases, this extends to global relevance.
- E-needs are mostly well taken care of. The RIs have data management plans and live up to the FAIR principles etc. Some distributed RI are still in a process of establishing a consistent framework for all nodes.
- Some of the RIs are in partnership with other RIs, leading to very useful collaboration, thereby enhancing the impact of the single infrastructures.
- All RIs seem to have recovered relatively well from the COVID-19 crisis, but some suffer negative impacts from geopolitical situations that exclude previous or potential partners, e.g. from Russia or Belarus.
- As in the previous batches, it is clear that many RIs are working on dealing with KPIs, at different levels. While many RIs have some specific KPIs that capture for instance access and scientific publications for some time, most Landmarks are still in the process of establishing a full KPI framework with a comprehensive view as suggested by the ESFRI KPI framework. Most RIs will need to invest more in collecting and categorising relevant data (related to numbers and origins of their users, publications, outreach, impact etc.) to be able to present complete and meaningful KPIs. Some RIs have difficulties when users do not physically access the RI, but use data and tools based on open platforms, so that quantification of relevant KPIs remains elusive and impact can only be shown via narratives.
- ESFRI Landmarks seem to find it difficult in some case how to choose relevant KPIs etc.
- Similarly, some Landmarks have difficulty describing the social or economic impact. Some Landmarks aim at long-term impact that is difficult to predict precisely. This is a task for ESFRI to take up.
- The main threat to the RIs (as perceived from their side) is their sustainability, e.g. in terms of insecurity about (long-term) membership of organisations and/or countries as well as the secured availability of funding. It is sometimes difficult for RIs to develop a policy in an environment where there is extremely strong competition for funding and where there is a lot of uncertainty about the evolution in the funding and support landscape, in particular, because RIs depend strongly on a long-term vision.
- A combination of long-term funding and project funding is common and useful, but a balance needs to be kept. An indicator “sustainability ratio” that divides long-term funding by project funding could be an interesting notion.
- Governance, management and HR policies are in general sound for the RIs, as is annual reporting, finances and audit etc.
- It may be difficult for RIs to find an overall aim or strategy in a quickly evolving society. RIs are expected to contribute strongly to relevant societal problems, but often they do not receive

adequate extra funding (and time) to build up that expertise, or activities must be done at the expense of shutting down other lines of research or competence.

Two Panels recommend revisiting the respective Landmarks soon, as at the time of monitoring the Landmarks were in a process of re-organization with major and unpredictable impact on their services and performance. While the two cases are very different, both underline the dynamic nature of RIs.

EXPERIENCES AND LESSONS LEARNT FROM THE FIRST ROUND OF ESFRI LANDMARK MONITORING

The MC collected the experience with the Landmark Monitoring procedure through all three batches. The results show that besides timing issues and workload, the process worked generally well. A number of practical issues were addressed following the experience with the first batch. While the later batches were already running more smoothly than the first batch, the experience of all batches underscores the necessity of early and succinct information for the Panels, experts and Landmarks. Generally, some continuity in Panel composition is advantageous. The Panel Chairs have an outstanding responsibility that can be best met with experience with ESFRI Landmarks and the ESFRI Landmark Monitoring procedures.

For this first full pilot round it was decided at the beginning that the Landmark status will not be questioned for any Landmark of the three batches in the pilot round. From the current experience, this was the correct decision due to the pilot character of the first round and, importantly, the need to build trust and acceptance for the Landmarks that should understand the Monitoring as both quality control and supportive advice. Nevertheless, in a very few cases for different reasons the Monitoring could not confirm good performance and fulfilment of the Minimal Key Requirements (MKR). These Landmarks should be revisited in the near future.

The Lessons Learnt (to be concluded in 2025) will contribute to optimising the monitoring procedure.

Organisation

Monitoring the third batch of ESFRI Landmarks followed the procedures of the first two batches and the same reporting format for Landmarks as was used for the second batch which was a revised version of the one used for the first batch.

For each Landmark, a Monitoring Panel was set up with a Chair from the relevant Strategy Working Group (SWG) and members from relevant SWGs, the DIGIT SWG and the Implementation Group (IG). Guidelines for the process, including timelines, document templates and questionnaires, were set up. The procedure was explained at online workshops that addressed Landmarks, Monitoring Panels and external experts in dedicated events. It was obvious that the time invested in explaining the aim, the methodology, the procedure and, importantly, answering questions was well spent.

Timing and interaction with Landmarks

The Monitoring Panels contacted the Landmarks in or around January 2024, and discussed the KPIs and other information that the Landmarks should provide. The Monitoring questionnaire to be filled out by the Landmarks was made available via the MOS+ system on 5th of March 2024. Information and documents were submitted by the Landmarks until 29th of April 2024. The process worked as established during the first two batches, and uploading in MOS+ and later on, of the reports in CIRCABC in general went smoothly. The external experts (for Scientific Case and Implementation Case) were contracted in February and March 2024, and they provided their assessment reports by the end of July 2024. Based on the reports of the external experts and on discussion of these report in the Monitoring Panels questions were drafted for the hearing of the Landmark. The hearings took place in September 2024. If necessary, a site visit was possible, and two Panels used this option. After the hearings, the Monitoring Panels drafted their reports and sent them to the Landmarks to check for any factual errors, following which the reports were finalised in the second half of October. The timing was quite tight, and monitoring tasks were spread unevenly across the Strategy Working Groups. Especially for the members of the IG and DIGIT, present in all Monitoring Panels, timing was challenging. In addition, the monitoring process took place at the same time as the Landscape Analysis was finalized, the new Roadmap 2026 process kicked off, and other drafting groups were active, so resources were very stretched, but most were able to manage the work within the set timeline. However, it is clear that the timeframe was too tight for all parties involved, and for subsequent monitoring exercises there should be more time and ESFRI should try to distribute the planning of events and requests a little better when possible.

LESSONS LEARNT

Questionnaire and format

- After the first batch, the submission format and process for the questionnaire was updated for the second and third batches. This new format worked better than for the first batch, but improvements may still be possible.
- It is good that the Panels discussed the KPIs and additional documents before the Landmarks filled out the questionnaire. This prior discussion allows the monitoring exercise to be put in perspective, both for the Landmark and for the Panel, and maybe more time and attention should be allowed for this step in the future, not least for the Landmarks.

Monitoring Panels

- The composition of each Monitoring Panel as it is established at the beginning, as well as any updates should consistently and immediately be communicated to the respective Panel Chair and all the members of this Monitoring Panel. Panel compositions have to be always available to the members of the Monitoring Committee, and changes in the Panel composition should be actively communicated (in either direction).
- The share of workload in the Panel between SWG members, members of the Implementation Group (IG) and DIGIT should be made clear.
- It is important that the Panel Chair is fully aware of the procedures (SWG Chair responsibility).
- It is advised that for a future Monitoring exercise the Panel Chairs are given more guidance on the details of their tasks and responsibilities by the SWG Chairs and the Monitoring Committee.
- The Panel Chairs are advised to inform all Panel members early on about the procedure and timeline and keep them updated on any steps taken, such as selecting and contracting experts and communicating with the Landmarks.
- There is one Panel for each Landmark, and it includes the SWG, DIGIT and IG members. They each concentrate on their respective part but they work together.
- The expectations of Panel members, experts and Landmarks should be clearly communicated to and by the Panel Chairs so that any doubts about the process and timing can be resolved quickly and clarifications provided.
- The process requires a high level of commitment from the SWG (including DIGIT) and IG members who are involved in the Monitoring Panels.
- The re-nomination procedure for SWGs and IG in the middle of the third batch was disruptive to the work of the Panels, fortunately with no impact on the Monitoring Reports.
- The capacity of the IG was compromised by the re-nomination procedure, but could be re-established to be able to do the work. It is important that there is a sufficient number of members of the IG, and the IG is stable.
- It was perceived positively that the members from the SWG and IG were working together early on, which was not always the case for the evaluation of proposals for the ESFRI Roadmap.

External experts

- The appointment and involvement of the external experts has to be communicated to the Chair of the Monitoring Panels and the IG representative as early as possible.
- If possible, external experts should be from different countries.
- The procedure for contacting external experts and arranging the communication with them, including collecting the conflict of interest forms, until final contracting by StR-ESFRI was heterogeneous between panels. While flexibility to react to the individual situation is good, the procedure for bringing in the external experts could be described better to avoid uncertainty and confusion in the process.

The Monitoring Report

- Landmarks are informed about what will happen with the report, who has access, and who is the owner.
- The summary reports for the three batches of the first round served their purpose by reporting on the first experience with the monitoring process and by identifying topics of a more general interest, like the need to work more on KPI frameworks. For the future Landmark Monitoring it should be discussed what information about the results ESFRI may publish.

ANNEX

List of Landmarks monitored in this first round (from first to third batch)

Landmarks of the first batch:

Domain	Name	Full name	Roadmap (Y)	Landmark (Y)	Operation start (Y)	Monitoring Year
ENE	ECCSEL ERIC	European Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage Laboratory Infrastructure	2008	2018	2016	2022
ENV	ICOS ERIC	Integrated Carbon Observation System	2006	2016	2016	2022
ENV	EURO-ARGO ERIC	European contribution to the international Argo Programme	2006	2016	2014	2022
H&F	BBMRI ERIC	Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure	2006	2016	2014	2022
H&F	ECRIN ERIC	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network	2006	2016	2014	2022
H&F	EATRIS ERIC	European Advanced Translational Research Infrastructure in Medicine	2006	2016	2013	2022
H&F	ELIXIR	A distributed infrastructure for life-science information	2006	2016	2014	2022
PSE	ESRF EBS	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility Extremely Brilliant Source	2006	2016	2020	2022
PSE	SPIRAL2	Système de Production d'Ions Radioactifs en Ligne de 2e génération	2006	2016	2019	2022
SSH	ESS ERIC	European Social Survey	2006	2016	2013	2022
SSH	CLARIN ERIC	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure	2006	2016	2012	2022

Landmarks of the second batch:

Domain	Name	Full name	Roadmap (Y)	Landmark (Y)	Operation start (Y)	Monitoring Year
ENV	EPOS	European Plate Observing System	2008	2018	2023	2023
ENV	EMSO ERIC	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water-column Observatory	2006	2016	2016	2023
ENV	IAGOS	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System	2006	2016	2014	2023

H&F	INFRAFRONTIER	European Research Infrastructure for the generation, phenotyping, archiving and distribution of mouse disease models	2006	2016	2013	2023
H&F	INSTRUCT ERIC	Integrated Structural Biology Infrastructure	2006	2016	2017	2023
H&F	Euro-Biolmaging ERIC	European Research Infrastructure for Imaging Technologies in Biological and Biomedical Sciences	2008	2018	2016	2023
H&F	EMBRC ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre	2008	2018	2017	2023
PSE	ILL	Institut Max von Laue-Paul Langevin	2006	2016	NA	2023
PSE	EMFL	European Magnetic Field Laboratory	2008	2016	2014	2023
SCI	SHARE ERIC	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe	2006	2016	2011	2023
SCI	DARIAH ERIC	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities	2006	2016	2019	2023

Landmarks of the third batch (this report):

Domain	Name	Full name	Roadmap (Y)	Landmark (Y)	Operation start (Y)	Monitoring Year
DIGIT	PRACE	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe	2006	2016	2010	2024
ENV	LifeWatch ERIC	e-Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research	2006	2016	2017	2024
ENV	EISCAT_3D	Next generation European Incoherent Scatter radar system	2008	2018	2023	2024
H&F	EU-OPENSREEN ERIC	European Infrastructure of Open Screening Platforms for Chemical Biology	2008	2018	2021	2024
H&F	ERINHA	European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents	2008	2018	2018	2024
PSE	European XFEL	European X-Ray Free-Electron Laser Facility	2006	2016	2017	2024
PSE	ELI ERIC	Extreme Light Infrastructure	2006	2016	2018	2024
SSH	CESSDA ERIC	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives	2006	2016	2013	2024